

MOUNTAINS UNCOVERED

Intercomparable Maps and Statistics for 100 Selected Global Mountain Ranges

Ural Mountains

#61

Ural Mountains

The *Mountains Uncovered* series has been developed by GEO Mountains to provide a set of easily understandable and inter-comparable maps, tables, and figures spanning a range of thematic areas for 100 selected global mountain ranges. This is the report for the **Ural Mountains** mountain range. The [index page](#) shows an overview of all mountain ranges in the series.

Location of the Ural Mountains mountain range [1][2].

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1. General Information

1.1. Administrative

The mountain range is fully within **Russia**, as shown in Figure 1.1. The overview is based on the GADM dataset [3] of administrative divisions at Level 0.

Figure 1.1. Administrative Overview

● Russia: 60,016 km² 100%

Map showing the administrative divisions overlapping with the mountain range.

Data: GADM [3] Background: GMBA [2], GADM [3], Natural Earth [3], Geonames [4], World Bank [22].

1.2. Demographics

Data on the mountain range's human population are sourced from the European Commission's GHS-POP dataset [5]. According to this source, it is estimated that **90,710** people lived in the area in 2020. This is expected to **increase to 91,286** by 2030. There are **no large settlements** listed in the populated places database.

In 2020, the human population in this mountain range was estimated to be 90,710.

Figure 1.2. Population estimates in the mountain range from 1975-2030. The data after 2020 are projections.

The maps show the population density in the mountain range (Figure 1.3), and estimated travel time to the nearest population centre with more than 50,000 inhabitants (Figure 1.4). Estimated travel time can be useful for evaluating accessibility to services and markets.

1.3. Development and Economic Indicators

The Human Development Index (HDI) is determined by a combination of indicators such as life expectancy, literacy rate, access to electricity, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and others. In 2015, the average HDI in this mountain range was estimated to be **0.83**. This is considered to be a **very high level of development**.

The total GDP within this mountain range in 2015 was estimated to be **\$2 billion**, an **increase of \$192 million since 2000**. Table 1.2. shows an overview of the HDI and GDP indicators over time.

Table 1.2. GDP and HDI Indicators over Time

	1990	2000	2015
Gross Domestic Product	\$3 bn	\$2 bn	\$2 bn
Human Development Index	0.75	0.74	0.83

Source: Kummu et al. [7]

1.4. Protected Areas

Figure 1.3 shows the spatial coverage of protected areas in the mountain range according to the World Database of Protected Areas (WDPA) [8]. A total of **40%** of the mountain range is covered by a protected area. The establishment of protected areas represents a key measure to protect and conserve valuable mountain biodiversity and ecosystems. These areas vary broadly in their aims, regulations, and effectiveness, however.

Figure 1.3. Protected Areas

A total of 40% of the mountain range is classified as protected in the World Database of Protected Areas.

The largest protected areas are:

1. Virgin Komi Forests	28,702 km ²
World Heritage Site (natural or mixed)	
2. Pechoro-Ilychskiy	7,077 km ²
UNESCO-MAB Biosphere Reserve	
3. Polyarno-Ural'skij	4,569 km ²
Natural Park	
4. Ilychskij	3,467 km ²
State Natural Zakaznik	
5. Synsko-Vojkarskij	2,900 km ²
State Natural Zakaznik	

2. Land cover

2.1. Land Cover

According to the ESA WorldCover dataset [9], the most dominant land cover types in 2021 were **tree cover (57.5%)**, **moss and lichen (24.4%)**, and **grassland (14.4%)**.

Figure 2.1. Land Cover

Land cover percentages from 2021 for the largest land cover classes in the mountain range.

The European Commission's Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) [10] classifies **0.0%** of the mountain range's area as urban centre, **0.1%** as urban cluster, and **99.9% as rural**.

3. Topography

The land surface elevation ranges from a **minimum of -30 m** to a **maximum of 1,894 m at Gora Narodnaya**. The **mean elevation is 584 m**. **50%** of the area lies is between **426 m and 717 m**, and **90%** of the area lies between **266 m and 879 m**. Figure 3.1 shows a shaded relief elevation map based on the MERIT DEM [11] and a selection of peaks from the Geonames dataset [4]. The distribution of land surface elevation strongly affects local climatic and living conditions in mountains.

Figure 3.1. Elevation and Peaks

Figure 3.2. Distribution of elevation within in the mountain range [11].

Figure 3.3. Distribution of slope steepness within in the mountain range [21].

Figure 3.4. Highest peaks in the mountain range according to the Geonames [4] dataset.

1. **Gora Narodnaya** ▲ 1,894 m
2. **Gora Manaraga** ▲ 1,662 m
3. **Gora Kolokol'nya** ▲ 1,640 m
4. **Gora Yamantau** ▲ 1,640 m
5. **Gora Telpoziz** ▲ 1,617 m
6. **Gora Bol'shoy Iremel'** ▲ 1,582 m
7. **Gora Konzhakovskiy Kamen'** ▲ 1,569 m
8. **Gora Kos'vinskiy Kamen'** ▲ 1,519 m
9. **Gora Denezhkin Kamen'** ▲ 1,492 m
10. **Gora Payer** ▲ 1,472 m

4. Climate

4.1. Temperature and Precipitation

Precipitation and temperature combine to control local weather and climate, with implications for water availability, vegetation growing conditions, snow and ice accumulation, and extreme events such as floods and droughts.

The mean annual temperature across the mountain range is shown in Figure 4.1. The **mean annual temperature for the entire mountain range is -4.0°C** , but it varies geographically from a **minimum of -11.4°C** to a **maximum of 4.1°C** . The temperature data are extracted from the CHELSA climatology dataset [13].

The mean annual precipitation shown in Figure 4.2. The **mean annual precipitation for the entire mountain range is 956 mm**, but it varies geographically from a **minimum of 348 mm** to a **maximum of 1,757**. Precipitation data are bias-corrected for use in mountain environments, and are extracted from CHELSA data in the Precipitation Bias CORrection (PBCOR) dataset [12].

Figure 4.1. Mean Annual Temperature

Figure 4.2. Mean Annual Precipitation

The mean monthly temperature across the entire mountain range shown in Figure 4.3, and varies from a **maximum of 13.6°C in July** to a **minimum of -19.1°C in January**. Equivalent statistics for precipitation are shown in Figure 4.4, which vary from a **maximum of 115 mm in July** to a **minimum of 47 mm in February**.

Figure 4.3. Mean Monthly Temperature

Data: CHELSA [13].

Figure 4.4. Mean Monthly Precipitation

Data: CHELSA/PBCOR [12].

4.2. Climate Classifications

Figures 4.5 and Figure 4.6 show Köppen-Geiger climate classifications for the present day (1980-2016) and for projected future conditions (2071-2100), respectively. Future conditions are derived from an ensemble of 32 climate model projections under the RCP 8.5 "business-as-usual" scenario [14].

Figure 4.5. Current Climate Classifications

Köppen-Geiger climate classification for the present day (1980-2016).

Data: GloH2O [14]. Background: GMBA [2], GADM [3], Natural Earth [3], Geonames [4], World Bank [22].

Figure 4.6. Future Climate Classifications

Köppen-Geiger climate classification for ensemble mean projected future conditions (2071-2100) under the RCP 8.5 scenario.

Data: GloH2O [14]. Background: GMBA [2], GADM [3], Natural Earth [3], Geonames [4], World Bank [22].

Table 4.1. Changes in climate classifications between current (1980-2016) and future (2071-2100) conditions

Classification	Current	Future	Change
Dfc Cold, no dry season, cold summer	81.7%	63.7%	▼ 18.0%
ET Polar, tundra	9.4%	0.0%	▼ 9.4%
Dfb Cold, no dry season, warm summer	8.9%	23.5%	▲ 14.6%
Dfa Cold, no dry season, hot summer	0.0%	12.7%	▲ 12.7%

Source: GloH2O [14].

5. Hydrology

According to the GRDC Major River Basins dataset, **four major basins** intersect the mountain range [15]. The **Ob has the most overlap with 39%** and drains into the **Kara Sea**.

Figure 5.1 shows major rivers and basins that intersect with this mountain range. The Global Reservoirs and Dams (GRaND) database does not contain any dams within this mountain range.

Figure 5.1. Major Rivers, Basins, and Dams.

Data: GRDC [15], GRaND [16]. Background: GMBA [2], GADM [3], Natural Earth [3], Geonames [4], World Bank [22].

6. Cryosphere

6.1. Glaciers and Permafrost

The Randolph Glacier Inventory dataset contains **161 glaciers** that intersect with this mountain range [17]. They cover a **total area of 14 km² (0.0%)**. In addition to the glaciers, it is estimated that under favourable conditions, permafrost occurrence is possible across **45,335 km² (75.5%)**, and is likely across at least **20,150 km² (33.6%)**. Figure 6.1 shows glaciers and permafrost extents. Glaciers and permafrost represent (largely non-renewable) water sources for mountain people and ecosystems, and can be implicated in hazardous events.

Figure 6.1. Glacier and Permafrost Extents

The Randolph Glacier Inventory lists **161 glaciers** within this mountain range, covering a **total area of 14 km²**.

6.2. Snow Cover

The average snow covered area in this mountain range is not shown because not enough data is available in particular months of the year. This can happen during winters at high latitudes, when lack of daylight results in fewer valid observations.

7. Measurement Locations

The GEO Mountains Inventory of In Situ Observational Infrastructure (v2.0) lists a total of **12 measurement sites** in this mountain range [20]. Their locations are shown as red dots in Figure 7.1. In situ measurements are crucial for a range of scientific and practical application in mountains, yet the locations of measurement sites are often difficult to gain an appreciation of. Measurement sites include weather and climate stations, river gauging stations, networks of stations, experimental basins, and others.

Figure 7.1. Locations of Measurement Sites

According to the GEO Mountains Inventory of In Situ Observational Infrastructure, there are 12 measurement sites in this mountain range

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Index

The index shows an overview of the 100 mountain ranges in version v1.0 of the *Mountains Uncovered* series.

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3. Drakensberg
4. Eastern Arc Mountains
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98. Meseta Patagónica
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100. Sierras Pampeanas

About the Series

Aims

The *Mountains Uncovered* series (v1.0) aims to provide an easily understandable overview of the key characteristics of 100 selected mountain ranges around the world. Comparisons between mountain ranges can also readily be made. The series was developed by collating and visualising a variety of current global scale data products. We hope that the series will be a useful resource for researchers, policy-makers, environmental managers, educators, and others seeking to better understand the Earth's major mountain regions, and that over time it will inspire the generation of additional datasets, analyses, and products.

Citation and Sharing

The *Mountains Uncovered* series (v1.0) has been developed on the basis of exclusively open global spatial datasets. In turn, all visualisations, statistics, and code generated are shared under the [Creative Commons BY 4.0](#) license. You may use, distribute, and reproduce the product in any medium, provided appropriate acknowledgement is given. Please cite the series as:

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GEO Mountains assumes no responsibility and accepts no liability for the product's use, and remains neutral with respect to the locations of any borders and the place names shown in the third-party datasets employed.

Limitations

Users should note that data and information are limited in many mountain regions around the world. As a result, the figures, maps, and graphs presented in this series are associated with uncertainties, and these uncertainties must be taken into account when interpreting the information given.

To ensure that any comparisons made between individual mountain ranges are as fair as possible, global-scale datasets were used (without any additional modification). Consequently, the series does not necessarily represent a compendium of the "best" data available in any given mountain range or local area, but rather a common, generally intercomparable set. For applications at local and regional scales, alternative datasets to those shown may be more suitable.

Indeed, in parallel to the ongoing development of the global series, more local and regional "bottom-up" engagements and activities to improve the quality and availability of data should also be undertaken, since data on these scales also play a crucial role in supporting decision-making for the benefit of mountain people and ecosystems.

Get Involved

While many global mountain regions remain notoriously data-scarce, new datasets are being released regularly. If you are aware of any datasets you would like us to consider including in a potential future release, please provide the necessary details via [this form](#). Likewise, if you become aware of any errors, omissions, or other potential modifications that could be made in a future version, please let us know via the same form. By taking these actions, you will help us expand the scope and improve the impact of the *Mountains Uncovered* series. Feedback concerning the underlying datasets will be collated and shared with the relevant organisations or data providers.

Contact

For any general queries or comments, please contact: geomountains@mountainresearchinitiative.org

Many thanks for your interest, support, and contributions to global mountain data, policy, and education!

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About GEO Mountains

GEO Mountains is an Initiative of the Group on Earth Observations (GEO). It aims to bring together research institutions and mountain observation networks to enhance the discoverability, accessibility, and use of a wide range of relevant data and information pertaining to environmental and socio-economic systems – both in situ and remotely sensed – across global mountain regions. In doing so, we hope to help facilitate scientific advancements and support decision makers at local, national, and regional levels. The figure below illustrates the scope of the Initiative.

GEO Mountains is an open and inclusive network. We aspire to follow the principles of open data and open science wherever possible.

